

Title: Transparent Affordance

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1. PROGRAM NOTES

Affordance describes the relationship between the environment and the individual from the action provider's perspective. Affordance can be false, can be hidden, or can be perceptible. Within our complex environment, real or virtual, material or intellectual, the affordances can be functional or delusional, can be ephemeral or permanent, can be present or delayed – a choice for you to observe, adapt, participate, and evolve.

Fig. 1. Performance picture

2. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Transparent Affordance is a real-time multichannel interactive electronic music composition of approximately six minutes in duration for iPad controllers, custom-made box, and Kyma.

Solving problems with the available resources has been vital for every aspect in life when the supply chain is interrupted since the beginning of the pandemic. Making use of what's available around us at home or locally encourages creative practitioners from different fields continue inspiring our community and the world around us close and far away. In this piece, the author created a new layer of affordance between the two the seemingly familiar objects – an iPad and an acrylic box. The new interactions generated when moving the two objects provided us opportunities to discover musical expression. New performative movements such as subtle tapping, rotating iPad on top of the box, iPad free fall inside of the box, etc., are all new interactions we not necessarily imagine with materials like glass, aluminum, and acrylic. Solving the coexistence of the new combinations encourage us to rethink the relationship between us and art, and the (un)familiar world around us.

3. PERFORMANCE NOTES

The composition can be presented in person or virtual with adaptations to any available platform the venue uses.

4. MEDIA LINK(S)

- Video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=K1c0M3XRmzE>